

The Influence of Self-Concept and Social Support with Emotional Maturity in College Students who are Raised by Single Mothers

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ABSTRAC

This study aims to determine the effect of self-concept and social support with emotional maturity in students who are raised by single mothers. Participants in this study totaled 81 students. Respondents in this study were obtained by purposive sampling technique. This research analysis technique uses multiple regression. Data measurement uses a scale of self-control, social support and emotional maturity. Based on the results of the study, it is known that the variables, namely self-control and social support, have an influence of 34% on emotional maturity in students who are raised by single mothers and 66% are influenced by other factors outside the study.

Keyword : Self-Control, Social Support and Emotional Maturity

Introduction

Adolescence is a transitional period from childhood to adulthood. At this time adolescents tend to experience various kinds of changes, both physical and psychological, which results in adolescents having many problems to face, both with themselves and with the surrounding environment with the surrounding environment. This is because adolescents are in a period of self-discovery. An individual who is in adolescence in the world of education is required to be able to be open and assertive in expressing his opinions, thoughts towards others without losing self-confidence in order to be able to display behavior that is considered appropriate or in accordance with people his age.

At this time adolescents feel psychological turmoil in two needs, namely physical needs such as eating, drinking, sexual urges, and psychological needs such as affection, security, freedom, and others. In line with the changes that occur in adolescents, they are also faced with tasks that are different from those of childhood. Individuals have developmental tasks that must be fulfilled. If these tasks are successfully completed, satisfaction, happiness, and acceptance from the environment will be achieved.

Every individual who is at the developmental stage of adolescence is required to be able to control and control their feelings in the process of developing towards emotional maturity. This does not mean that a teenager must control all emotional turmoil that arises. Adolescents are expected to understand and master their emotions, so that they can achieve adaptive emotional conditions (Paramitasari & Alvian, 2012). The emotional maturity that exists in adolescents allows them to develop healthy relationships with their social environment. In this healthy relationship, adolescents will be able to manage their emotions, adjust to the atmosphere of others, and seek harmony in relationships with others (Mahmoudi, 2012).

Self-concept is not an innate factor, but develops from continuous and differentiated experiences. The basis of self-concept should be instilled early in a child's life so that it becomes the basis that influences his behavior in the future (Agustiani, 2006). In general, adolescents who have a positive self-concept can have high self-confidence, are not inferior and are not anxious when interacting with others. in contrast to adolescents who have a negative self-concept they will tend to feel unsure of themselves, feel weak, and feel inferior when interacting with others.

One of the factors that influence emotional maturity and self-concept is the existence of positive relationships with other people, because with these positive relationships, they will get social support and emotional closeness. Basically, the need to interact with others is an innate need.

Social support according to Sarafino (2006) is a feeling of comfort, attention, appreciation, or assistance received from other people or groups. Sarafino added that people who receive social support have the belief that they are loved, valuable and are part of a group that can help them when they need help. According to Orford (1992) social support works with the aim of minimizing the influence of pressures or stress experienced by individuals. In other words, if there is no pressure or stress, social support has no effect.

The existence of social support from family, relatives, and also other people can strengthen children in dealing with everyday life. For example, individuals who experience a problem really need people who can give them encouragement, motivation, advice and input that can help them get out of the problems they face. Parental support reflects the responsiveness of parents to children's needs, which is very important for children. Ellis, Thomas and Rollins (1976) define parental support as interactions developed by parents that are characterized by care, warmth, approval, and various positive feelings of parents towards children. Parental support makes children feel comfortable with the presence of parents and

confirms in the child's mind that he/she is accepted and recognized as an individual (Larsen & Dehle, 2007; Young, Miller, Norton & Hill, 1995).

However, not all children have an intact family. Some children only have one parent due to death or divorce. This event certainly has an impact on children. Children are certainly more vulnerable to stress due to the loss of one parent. Grief reactions that arise from death, such as shock, anger, withdrawal, sadness, or even suicide can be caused by immaturity in understanding and dealing with death, cultural factors, and lack of experience in adolescents (Wadsworth, 1984). Adolescents living with single parents will experience various psychological conflicts such as self-adjustment and social adaptation, emotional maturity, achievement motivation, ability to overcome difficulties and other psychological conflicts. The loss of one parent provides changes in the family.

Nolen-Hoeksema (1988) also suggested that adolescents have high levels of depression and adults show lower levels of depression (cited by Ehrlich & Isacowitz, 2002). Mistakes in understanding and handling psychological turmoil in adolescents can have fatal consequences, such as social disorientation in adolescents. Therefore, it needs support from all parties, especially parents, teachers, friends, and the social environment to help facilitate the psychological development of adolescents towards the adult world.

Previous research related to emotional maturity mostly examines with self-adjustment. Therefore, researchers are interested in taking other variables that may also have the same relationship as previous research. Based on the background of the problem above, the authors are interested in examining "The Relationship Between Self-Concept and Social Support with Emotional Maturity in Students Raised by Single Mothers".

RESEARCH METHODS

Participants

In this study, a population and sample problem is one of the important factors that must be considered. Population is the whole research subject (Arikunto, 2006). The total subjects who participated in this study were 81 people, the research sample was students who were studying at the university level at both undergraduate and postgraduate levels in several cities in Indonesia who were raised by single mothers with an age range of 19-36 years. The sample is part of the population that can represent the characteristics of the existing population (Azwar, 1998, p. 79). The sample must have at least one common trait, both nature and specialization (Sugiyono, 1999). In this study, the sampling technique used purposive sampling technique,

which is a sampling technique by selecting samples among the population according to the researcher's wishes (objectives / problems in the study) (Nursalam, 2008). Thus, the researcher took a sample with the criteria, namely undergraduate and postgraduate students who were raised by single mothers. Based on this number, 50 of them were women, and 31 of them were women. The age range of the participants was between 19 to 36 years old.

Design

This research includes correlational quantitative research. The independent variables in this study are self-concept, social support and the dependent variable is emotional maturity.

Measurement Tools

Emotional Maturity. The emotional maturity scale was taken and modified from Rosikhotul Ulum's (2017) research with aspects of emotional maturity according to Walgito (2004), namely first being able to accept the state of himself and others, not being impulsive, being able to control emotions, thinking objectively and having responsibility. The number of items is 23 statement items consisting of 15 favorable items and 8 unfavorable items. Questionnaire with Likert scale model with alternative answers from "very appropriate" to "very inappropriate".

Self-Concept. Aspects of Hurlock's (1996) self-concept were broken down into 23 items to measure physical, psychological, social, emotional, aspiration and achievement self-concept. The favorable and unfavorable items are scaled on a 5-point continuum of strongly agree to strongly disagree. Example of an item "Many friends allow me to get to know various characters of people."

Social Support. The social support scale consists of 17 statements which are divided into 18 favorable statements and 18 unfavorable statements. Questionnaire with Likert scale model with alternative answers from "very appropriate" to "very inappropriate".

Analysis Technique

Data analysis used in this study is a multiple regression analysis technique that aims to determine the effect of self-control (X1) and social support (X2) on emotional maturity (Y1) in students who are raised by single mothers. Data analysis using the help of the Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) for Windows version 25.0 program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Data

Description	Amount	Persentase
Gender		
Male	50	61,7%
Female	31	38,3%
Education		
S1	53	66,5%
S2	28	34,5 %

Based on descriptive analysis for self-concept data, it shows that the empirical mean ($\bar{x} = 55.32$) is higher than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 46$) which indicates that the self-concept in students who are raised by single mothers is in the moderate category. Descriptive analysis for social support data shows that the empirical mean ($\bar{x} = 35.8$) is higher than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 34$) which indicates that the self-concept in students who are raised by single mothers is in the moderate category. Descriptive analysis for social maturity data shows that the empirical mean ($\bar{x} = 45.59$) is higher than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 38$) which indicates that emotional maturity in students who are raised by single mothers is in the moderate category.

The results of the mean calculation based on the age of the subject, it is known that there are differences in self-concept, social support and emotional maturity owned by participants. results and categories based on age can be seen in Table 2. Mean subject descriptions based on gender are listed in Table 3.

Table 2. Mean and Category by Participant Age

Age	Self Concept	Social Support	Emotional Maturity
19 – 24	34,5 (moderate)	42,45 (high)	27,36 (moderate)
25 – 30	40, 23 (moderate)	34, 65 (moderate)	30, 78 (modrate)
31 - 36	43, 01 (high)	48, 23 (high)	47,52 (moderate)

Table 3. Mean and Category by Gender

Gender	Self Concept	Social Support	Emotional Maturity
Male	53,58 (moderate)	36,45 (moderate)	43,9 (moderate)
Female	55,68 (moderate)	43, 46 (moderate)	47,5 (high)

Table 4. Normality Test Result

Variabel	Sig.
Self Concept	0.000
Social Support	0.003
Emotional Maturity	0.000

Based on the normality test that has been carried out on the self-concept variable obtained α of 0.000, for social support of 0.003 and for emotional maturity of 0.000. Data distribution can be said to be normal if the significance value is greater than 0.05 ($\alpha > 0.05$). Therefore, the variables of self-concept, social support and emotional maturity are not normally distributed (not symmetrical).

Table 5. Regression Test Results

F	Sig.	R	R Square
20.492	0.000	0.587	0.344

Based on the results of the analysis based on table 5, it can be seen that there is a significant influence of self-concept and social support on emotional maturity. The regression test results show that the value of $F = 20.492$ with a significance of 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.05$), the value of $R = 0.587$ (58%) and the value of R square 0.344 (34%).

Table 6. Regression coefficient of self-concept and social support on emotional maturity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	17.078	4.116			4.149	.000
Self Concept	-.197	.078	-.265		-2.539	.013
Social Support	.501	.079	.665		6.376	.000

Based on table 5, it can be seen that the significance coefficient on the self-concept variable is 0.013 with $\alpha = 0.665$ (or 66%). And the significance coefficient value on the social support variable is 0.000 with $\alpha = -0.265$ (or -26%). This shows that these variables together have an influence on the emotional maturity variable.

Based on the results of this analysis, the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted. Teenagers or individuals with mature emotions are able to maintain emotional impulses, understand their own emotions to be directed towards positive actions, do not depend on others, are aware and responsible for carrying out decisions, accept weaknesses and strengths and accept themselves physically and psychologically well. The aspect of emotional maturity that theoretically exists in self-concept is the aspect of self-control, namely in the aspect of emotional self-concept. Adolescents' descriptions of their emotions, such as the ability to withstand emotions, angry, sad, or cheerful, vindictive, and forgiving are theoretically aspects of self-control in emotional maturity (Suroso, 2013).

This is also in line with the theory put forward by Lestari (2013) that parental support is proven to have a positive impact on life satisfaction. Social support aims to improve well-being, existence, and can provide assistance, encouragement, acceptance, and attention to individuals so that it can be said that someone already has good emotional maturity. A person will feel happy with the support he receives from family, friends, thus making the individual feel more confident and feel more meaningful, thus the individual gets acceptance from the environment which allows him to make meaning of life. This can be further explained by the results of research conducted by Fajarwati (2014) that social support from friends is the source of social support that has the highest influence on adolescents. The highest support in adolescents is also obtained from peers because during adolescence, adolescents spend a lot of time outside the home and are close to groups (Hurlock, 1998).

Even in adolescents who have a single parent, parents still support their children in doing all positive things so that the subject still feels supported. This can be seen by how individual emotional maturity assesses situations critically before reacting emotionally, not reacting without thinking beforehand like children or immature people. Thus adolescents can ignore stimuli that can cause emotional outbursts, which in turn can provide stable emotional reactions, not changing from one emotion or mood to another. Therefore, it is likely that students who have good emotional maturity will be able to control themselves well even with singleparent parents.

Other factors that influence emotional maturity include temperament, nature, personal character, income, socio-cultural influences and differences in separation experienced by parents due to death and divorce. This is in line with research conducted by Erni Sawitri (2017) which says that there are differences in adolescents who are raised from parents due to death

and divorce. Although it is obtained equally well in emotional maturity because when venting emotions does not harm others, it is different in subjects from families raised by single parent parents due to divorce when their emotional boundaries are disturbed, the release will hurt themselves, and shout, in contrast to subjects who are raised because their parents died, they will be more silent, self-introspection, and surrender to God because they think that if they act a lot, there will be many negative impacts obtained. As stated in Hetherington's research, stating that divorce events cause emotional instability, experiencing anxiety, depression, and frequent anger.

Emotional maturity can be said to be good if someone does not explode their emotions in front of others but waits for a more appropriate time and place. This is in accordance with the factors that cause emotional maturity, first, being able to express love. second, the ability to overcome tension. third, tolerance for frustration and fourth, attitudes in emotional control.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that the self-concept in students who are raised by single mothers is in the moderate category, social support and emotional maturity are in the moderate category. This gives a significant influence between self-control and social support on emotional maturity in students who are raised by single mothers. The amount of influence given by the two variables is as much as R square 34%, which is quite significant. There is about 42% influence obtained from other factors outside the study. Further research can be conducted to explore other factors that can affect emotional maturity in students who are raised by single mothers.

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